

Impact of Harassment on Work Basic Need Satisfaction of Women Working in Media Houses

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Abstract

The primary goal of the present research was to examine the Sexual harassment and its effects on work basic need satisfaction among women employees of media houses. Current study explored the role of workplace environment in relationship with harassment and work basic need satisfaction. Further the study explored the demographic differences across association between non-verbal harassment and work basic need satisfaction. Descriptive research design was used for present study. Sample drawn from G Power was comprised of (N=150) from the media houses of Multan and Lahore. Purposive sampling technique was used and convenient sampling was used to recruit data. Data was collected by using survey method through Work Harassment scale (Björkqvist & Österman, 1998), Work Basic Need Satisfaction Scale (Deci et al., 2001). After coding data was entered and then analyzed with the help of SPSS software. Findings showed that there is significant relationship of the sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction. As per to hierarchy theory of needs by Maslow if the safety needs of employee are considered only then they can have satisfaction. Process theory described it well how the process of behavior is energized, directed, sustained, and stopped in a certain workplace environment. Moreover, Preliminary Analysis revealed that there is no significant difference of marital status of harassment and work basic needs satisfaction. Implications of the present study along with its limitations were discussed and recommendations for future research were suggested.

Keywords: Sexual Harassment, Media houses, Job satisfaction, working women

1. Introduction

The issues of non-verbal harassment and work satisfaction had received very little attention in the literature. Minimal effort had been made to describe the phenomena of sexual harassment in relation to job satisfaction. This study research in terms of problems faced by working women in media houses. It is the hot issue that as being the developing country due to social restrictions and family matters they already have faced low job satisfaction rate. Meanwhile workplace environment effect their mental health and job performance. The aim of investigation was to fill a short part in scientific inquiry in this part of world. The goal of this study was to make a small contribution to better understanding current sexual harassment in Pakistani media outlets. In particular, it looked at the extent to which sexual harassment has occurred in the workplace as well as determining the correlation between sexual harassment and basic need satisfaction at work.

1.1. Harassment

Harassment means any unwelcome sexual advance, request for sexual favors or other verbal or written communication or physical conduct of a sexual nature or sexually demeaning attitudes, causing interference with work performance or creating an intimidating, hostile or offensive work environment, or the attempt to punish the complainant for refusal to comply to such a request or is made a condition for employment (PEMRA, 2010).

Sexual harassment may take these forms (Raver & Nishii, 2010).

- i. **Quid Pro Quo**, when a job benefit - such as a pay rise, a promotion, or even continued employment - is made conditional on the victim acceding to demands to engage in some form of sexual behavior; or;
- ii. **Verbal Harassment** It entails Comments and questions about appearance, life-style, sexual orientation, offensive phone calls
- iii. **Non –verbal Harassment** includes Whistling, sexually-suggestive gestures, and display of sexual materials.

The phenomenon of verbal harassment which entails sexual harassment has been studied in the present study. Harassment against women plagues all societies and needs to be eliminated in all its forms (Gupta & Garg, 2020). All space must be made safe for women and girls in the family, workplace, other private and public institutions including in police stations, lock-ups and jails, and public spaces in general. Harassment against women persists because of cultural norms and attitudes that condone such acts, inadequate laws and access to shelters that fail to protect women from violence and/or to provide relief and justice to survivors of violence (Sadruddin, 2013).

1.2. Work Basic Need Satisfaction

The concept of need is one that is fundamental to behavioral science (Latham & Budworth, 2006). Indeed, as early as 1938, Murray had postulated the existence of several social needs, such as the need for relatedness and the need for power. Basic needs refer to a set of innate and universal needs that must be fulfilled for optimal human functioning and development (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Maslow (1943) first introduced the concept, proposing that humans are motivated by five basic needs: physiological, safety, love, esteem, and self-actualization. Since Maslow's (1943) seminal work, others have proposed their own lists of basic needs. Deci and Ryan (1985)

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explained human motivation in terms of the need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness Hoppock defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job (Hoppock, 1935). According to this approach although job satisfaction is under the influence of many external factors, it remains something internal that has to do with the way how the employee feels. That is job satisfaction presents a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction. Vroom in his definition on job satisfaction focuses on the role of the employee in the workplace. Thus, he defines job satisfaction as affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying (Vroom, 1964). One of the most often cited definitions on job satisfaction is the one given by Spector (1997) according to whom job satisfaction has to do with the way how people feel about their job and its various aspects.

1.3. Hierarchy of Needs

Although commonly known in the human motivation literature, Maslow's needs hierarchy theory was one of the first theories to examine the important contributors to job satisfaction. The theory suggests that human needs form a five-level hierarchy consisting of physiological needs, safety, and belongingness/love, esteem, and self-actualization. Maslow's needs hierarchy was developed to explain human motivation in general. However, its main tenants are applicable to the work setting and have been used to explain job satisfaction. Within an organization, financial compensation and healthcare are some of the benefits which help an employee meet their basic physiological needs. Safety needs can manifest itself through employees feeling physically safe in their work environment, as well as job security. When this is satisfied, the employees can focus on feeling as though they belong to the workplace. This can come in the form of positive relationships with colleagues and supervisors in the workplace. Once satisfied, the employee will seek to feel as though they are valued and appreciated by their colleagues and their organization. The final step is where the employee seeks to self-actualize; where they need to grow and develop in order to become everything they are capable of becoming (McLeod, 2007).

1.4. Process Theory

Process theory describes the process of how behavior is energized, directed, sustained, and stopped. Process theory sees job satisfaction as being determined not only by the nature of the job and its context within the organization but also by the needs, values, and expectations that the individuals have in relation to their job (Bowling et al., 2005)

1.5. Two-Factor Theory (Motivator-Hygiene Theory)

Frederick Herzberg's two factor theory (also known as Motivator Hygiene Theory) attempts to explain satisfaction and motivation in the workplace. This theory states that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are driven by different factors - motivation and hygiene factors, respectively. An employee's motivation to work is continually related to job satisfaction of a subordinate (Hoskinson, Porter & Wrench, 2013). Motivating factors are those aspects of the job that make people feel secure in an environment and to perform in work and recognition. These motivating factors are considered to be intrinsic to the job, or the work carried out. Hygiene factors include aspects of the working environment such as pay, company policies, supervisory practices and other working conditions.

1.6. Affect Theory

Edwin A. Locke's Range of Affect Theory (1976) is arguably the most famous job satisfaction model. The main premise of this theory is that satisfaction is determined by a discrepancy between what one wants in a job and what one has in a job. Further, the theory states that how much one is feel secured moderates how satisfied/dissatisfied one becomes when expectations are/aren't met. When a person values a particular facet of a job, his satisfaction is more greatly impacted both positively (when expectations are met) and negatively (when expectations are not met), compared to one who doesn't value that facet. To illustrate, if Employee does not feel secure or being listened it will impact on their satisfaction about job. Further studies found that sexual harassment to be a significant predictor to decrease job satisfaction and increase work stress in the workplace. The results showed similarities with Fister- Gale (2003), Kronos Incorporated (2005), Merkin (2008) and Wolfe (1 994) which show that there are approximately 2.8 million lost work days each year due to job dissatisfaction and stress, which made up the overall absenteeism measure, were higher for employees experiencing sexual harassment than for employees not experiencing sexual harassment.

2. Review of Literature

Sexual harassment is an unwanted sex-based behavior that is used as a condition of employment or creates a hostile work environment for targets. Sexual harassment includes gender harassment (nonsexual gender based experiences, such as comments that women are incompetent), unwanted sexual attention (unsolicited sex-based comments, gestures, or attempts at physical contact), and sexual coercion (quid pro quo; job related threats or benefits used to compel sexual cooperation (Fitzgerald & Cortina, 2018).

Workplace sexual harassment has been shown to be responsible for undermining job satisfaction and affective commitment (Shaffer et al., 2002); as well as responsible for negative psychological conditions such as stress, depression and decrease productivity (Cortina et al., 2006; Idrees & Malik, 2022).

A study was done on sexual harassment in Britain which found out Superior/subordinate harassment is the most serious problem for women in "feminine" occupations, the real problem being posed by middle-class men with

higher occupational status. Co-worker harassment is more of a problem for middle-class women in management and professions, these women being in direct competition with middle-class men who cannot use occupational power over them (Heather Hemming, 2013; Haider and Ali, 2015; Kassem et al., 2019).

Incidence rates of sexual harassment of mass communication interns, and compared those rates to student and professional rates. A probability sample of 44 male and 52 female mass communications professionals was generated using several random sampling techniques from among professionals who work in Tampa, Florida and who completed a mass communication internship program while an undergraduate or graduate student. Results indicated that women experienced more incidents of sexual harassment than men in all three roles, but the difference was only statistically significant for professionals and professional experience more negatively than those who were not sexually harassed (Bowen & Laurion, 1994).

Given that the socio-cultural, religious, and economic contexts within Western and Islamic contexts are substantially different (Syed, 2008), Pakistani laws and their cultural enactment correspond in kind. Clear provisions exist in both Islam and the 1973 Pakistani Constitution to provide respect, safety, and equal rights for women; however, Pakistan remains a male-dominated culture where women still struggle to attain their rights (Akhtar & Métraux, 2013; Kazim & Rafique, 2021). Though sexual harassment is not clearly defined in Pakistan, it accompanies other violent acts against women such as honor killing, acid throwing, bride burning, domestic violence, denial of property, rape, human trafficking, trafficking for forced labour and sex, child marriages, obscene phone calls, torture, and the exchange of females to settle disputes (Nosheen, 2011). At times, Pakistani women are even suppressed and victimized by their own family members (Ghazal et al., 2022).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study was Descriptive research, and a survey research design was adapted to describe the relationship between Sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction among working women of Media. Further the study has explored the demographic differences across association between Sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction

3.2. Sample

Purposive sampling technique was used and Data was collected through convenient sampling technique. Sample drawn from G Power was comprised of (N=150) from the media houses of Multan and Lahore. Age range of participants varies from 20-35 years.

3.3. Instruments

Work Harassment scale (Björkqvist & Österman, 1998), Work Basic Need Satisfaction Scale (Deci et al., 2001) were used to measure sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction respectively.

3.4. Hypotheses

There is likely to be a relationship between sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction among working women of media.

There is likely to be a significant difference of marital status in sexual harassment and basic need satisfaction at work.

4. Results

Table1: Correlation

Scales	work basic need satisfaction	Sexual harassment
Basic need satisfaction	1	-.193*
Sexual Harassment		1

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$

Table 1 explores that relationship between study variables. It indicated that Sexual harassment had a significant negative correlation with Work basic need satisfaction.

Table 2: Means, Standard Deviation, t-values of Differences w,r,t, Marital Status

	Marital status	N	Mean	SD	t	p-value
Basic need satisfaction	single	96	3.4673	.47706	-.764	.446
	married	54	3.5300	.49167		
Workplace Harassment	single	96	2.0651	.33978	-.116	.908
	Married	54	2.0586	.30517		

Note: N=150, $p > 0.05$

An independent sample t-test was used to compare the difference of marital status Table 2 revealed that there are no significant differences of marital status on harassment and work basic need satisfaction among working women of media.

5. Discussion

Current study explored the role of workplace environment in relationship with harassment and work basic need satisfaction. Further the study explored the demographic differences across association between non-verbal harassment and work basic need satisfaction. To be a working woman in Pakistan is not such easy. Women are excluded from top positions, outnumbered by men Favoring male reporters, Sexual harassment Tradition and cultural hindrance Unfriendly and lack of encouragement environment Long and predictable hours carry a social stigma for women. Improper workplace environment Low pay package. By keeping in mind all these possibilities, it was hypothesized that Sexual harassment and work basic need satisfaction co-related to each other. According to the results of the study both are having negative co-relation (See table 1). The findings after the research on impact of harassment and work basic need satisfaction among women showed that there is negative significant relationship of the harassment and work basic need satisfaction. If harassment increases at workplace the level of work basic need satisfaction gets low.

Media houses are not meeting the basic needs of women, though now women in field of journalism enhance with time. Media houses needs to create a safe working environment for women, which is free of harassment, abuse and intimidation with a view toward fulfillment of their right to work with dignity. It will also enable higher productivity and a better quality of life at work. Harassment is one of the biggest hurdles faced by working women preventing many who want to work to get themselves and their families out of poverty in Pakistan (PEMRA, 2010).

As per to hierarchy theory of needs by Maslow if the safety needs of employee is considered only then they can have satisfaction and establish self-actualization about themselves. Apart from the company policy and administration role in job satisfaction, Physical working conditions and securities are much significant for job satisfaction of women employees. These should be framed in keeping the view of employee's needs and desire. All family, work, and other private and governmental institutions, including all media outlets, must be made safe for women and girls so they can contribute their best and improve the caliber of news. Even though it is married or unmarried the women must have the right to feel secure in working place. That's why it was hypothesized that either married men face sexual harassment more or unmarried women. Results revealed that there is no significant difference of marital status of sexual harassment and work basic needs satisfaction (See Table 2).

In Pakistan female employees working in the formal sector, in media organizations, reported that they faced sexual harassment in the workplace (AASHA, 2002). Victims faced both quid pro quo and hostile environment. For example, most victims were asked to go out by co-workers and employers, threatened when they refused to comply with sexual propositions by their bosses, and faced sexually suggestive comments. Different environmental factors like COVID-19 pandemic have also affected the sexual harassment behaviors. COVID-19 pandemic has affected the health-related behaviors (Asif et al., 2020; Idrees et al., 2022) as well as technology facilitated sexual harassment (Jatmiko et al., 2020).

6. Conclusion

It is concluded that Workplace environment keeps a huge volume in the job satisfaction of employees. Women faced sexual harassment in the media workplace which in turn low the work basic need satisfaction among them it lead towards turnover and overall productivity of a country effects due to this reason. There should be debate and awareness campaigns to highlight the issue regarding sexual harassment women face at the media houses regardless of their marital status. In order to ensure that women can exercise their right to a workplace that is free from harassment, abuse, and intimidation, media organizations must do so.

6.1. Strengths

The strengths of the study are:

- i. It focused on the pertinent issues of the working women who dare to work in the media houses.
- ii. The preset study highlighted the major issues which are hurdles in workspace for women.
- iii. This study worked out of the box and focuses on sensitive issue of sexual harassment of the country.

6.2. Limitations

- i. The study had limited resources and a large sample should have entailed for the purpose of the current research.
- ii. There were some cultural differences which affected my research study.
- iii. There was limited time for conducting the research which also affected the research study.

6.3. Implications

- i. The study focused on the awareness for the safe working environment for women in media houses.
- ii. In terms of research, this study provided an indigenous perspective on ongoing issue of working women who want to contribute in economy of Pakistan but needs a safe environment it may pave the way for future research in this under-researched area.
- iii. This study provided ground for organizational psychologists to work and resolves such issues from organizations.

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